

Impact of Multimedia Aids on Performance and Retention in Chemistry among Secondary School Students in Funtua Educational Zone, Katsina State.

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Abstract

This study examined the Impact of Multimedia aids on Performance and Retention in Chemistry Secondary School Students in Funtua Educational Zone, Katsina State. Two objectives, two corresponding research questions and two null hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted Quasi-experimental research design specifically, pretest, post-test and post-post-test, non-equivalent control group. The study has a population of two thousand one hundred and eighty-seven (2187) SS II chemistry students during the 2023/2024 academic session in Funtua Education zone in Katsina state and a sample size of 177 students in two intact classes were selected by cluster sampling from two schools in the local government area and used for the study. Chemistry performance test (CPT) was used to elicit response for the study, the CPT was validated by three experts and subsequently pilot tested to determine its reliability index. Hence, reliability index of 0.86 was obtained using test-retest method which implies that the instrument is reliable for the study. The stated research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation statistics and null hypotheses were tested using an independent sample t-test at 0.05 level of significance. The finding of the study revealed that a significant difference exists in the mean academic performance and retention scores of SS II students taught Chemistry concept using Multimedia aids and those taught using conventional method. It was concluded that Multimedia aids improve performance and retention. It was also recommended that Science teachers should incorporate the use Multimedia aids in Chemistry and other science subjects. Multimedia aids should be incorporated in the curriculum of teacher training institutions to promote retention ability in Chemistry.

Keywords: Multimedia aids aid, Performance, Retention, Chemistry Concepts.

Introduction

Education according to Bello (2017) is conceived as the process of learning to live as a useful and acceptable member citizen of a community and a good citizen of a country. This process starts from the moment a person is born to death and it involves a number of activities by several people such as teachers, students, parents, government and all citizens of a country. It is also conceived as the development of the totality of man and natural world implying that, through education, man develops mentally, morally and spiritually (Georgewill, 2006). In view of these educators' conceptions and explanations, it could rightly be inferred that education is an umbrella (mother) body comprising of various disciplines such as art, technical, vocation, social science and science education.

Science as a concept is a process that is geared aimed at problem solving in order to enhance the living standard of man. Science can be regarded as a dynamic and objective process of seeking knowledge which involves scientist in the process of searching, investigating and seeking verification of natural things occurring in the environment (Nworgu, 2012). Nwagbo (2011) defined science as an intellectual activity carried out by human and designed to discuss information about the natural world in which he lives as well as to discover the ways in which the information can be organized to benefit human race. It can also be seen in terms of method and process as well as products comprising facts, concept, principles and laws that make up the body of science. From these views' students learning science are placed in problem solving situation. Owolabi (2012) views science as an integral part of human society. Its impact is felt in every way of human life so much that it is intricately linked with a nation's development. There are five basic branches of science in secondary school curriculum: these are Chemistry, Chemistry, Geography, Mathematics and Physics.

Science education deals with sharing of science content and process with individuals who are not considered traditionally to be members of the scientific community, the individuals could be students, farmers, market women or a whole community. The major aim science teaching is to promote the understanding of the concept being taught with a view of applying knowledge of such understanding to real life situation (Ogunbowale, 2014). The objectives of science education in Nigeria, according to Maduekwe (2006) include: the need to prepare students to observe and explore the environment, explain simple natural phenomena, develop scientific attitudes including curiosity, critical reflection and objectivity, apply the skills and knowledge gained through science to solve everyday problems in the environment, develop self-confidence and self-reliance through problems solving activities in science.

Chemistry as one of the branches of science deals with the nature of matter, its properties and its change in different conditions. Tajudeen (2019) define chemistry as the science that deals with structure and composition of matter. Chemistry according to Omoniyi (2014) should be studied to improve man's knowledge and enhance the understanding of the environment for survival. (Aniodoh & Egbo, 2013) observed that the importance of chemistry can be felt in almost all sphere of our national life. Therefore, chemistry education has a fundamental role to play in providing solution to several technological and socio-economic issues confronting man as well as improving scientific literacy (Ezeliora, 2010).

Many research findings such as that of Ajaja (2009) and Ahmed (2010) on the Chemistry teaching in Nigeria has revealed that, chemistry as a subject is poorly taught because of the use of inappropriate method of teaching such as lecture method (Johnson, 2018). In spite of the importance of chemistry in our national development and the effort being made by government, researchers, Science Teachers Association of Nigeria and other agencies, students' performance has been very poor and unsatisfactory year after year. Over 50% of the students perceived chemistry as a body of isolated fact to be memorized, lacking relevance to reality which has led to lack of interest in it by students. For many students, chemistry is a classroom affair. However, studies such as that of Njoku (2011) and that of West African Examination Council Chief Examiners Report (WAEC, 2023) revealed that, academic performance of students in chemistry at Senior School Certificate Examination (SSCE) has been very low.

Many factors have been suggested as contributing to this low academic performance of students particularly in chemistry and science in general, some of these factors includes; poor teaching methods, inadequate facilities and inadequate laboratory infrastructure for teaching chemistry (Tami, 2014) Result of several researchers conducted over the years had indicated that of all the various factors responsible for low performance in chemistry, poor teaching method was the most predominant (Mari, 2014). One of the problems in implementing science curriculum has been the use of inadequate approach or instructional strategy for the teaching of chemistry concepts. A lot of emphasis has been placed on this by the experimental science curriculum projects at both international and local levels. But despite the amount of effort and emphasis, science teachers in Nigeria schools still revert to the use of lecture method for teaching, as conventional method, is didactic, stereotype and non-result oriented. It is often described as "talk and chalk" method because its presents information to the students who merely listen. Teacher does all the talk while students listening and copy note on the chalkboard after the lesson (Akpoghol *et al.*, 2016). This teacher-centered approach dominates the educational system in Nigeria except few private schools that are well equipped with modern Information and Communication Technology (ICT) facilities such as computer laboratories with computers and internet facilities, interactive whiteboards, learning software, Multimedia aids, and many others. Consequently, research results have shown that the use of innovative teaching method such as Multimedia aids instructional strategy could enhance performance and retention in science, including chemistry (Osman and Vebrianto, 2013; Rohaida and Kamariah 2005).

Multimedia aids is the combination of instructional methods that encourage learners to engage in active learning by mentally representing materials in words and pictures making connections between the pictorial and verbal representations (Clark and Mayer cited in Krishnasamy, 2007). Kumar (2013) asserted that Multimedia aids are instructional materials and interactive application that integrate text, colour, graphic images, audio, animation, audio sound, and full motion video in a single application. According to Adekunmisi (2012) opined that Multimedia aids could be interpreted as a combination of data carriers, such as video, CD-ROM, floppy disks, Internet and software in which the possibility for an interactive approach is offered. Multimedia aids instructional package consists of resources which are computer-based with text, pictures, sound, animation, video or a combination of these media used in educational instruction to enhance learning outcome (Mayer, 2013). Multimedia aids instruction can convey information in a stimulating situation that aids the brain to preserved and information in the form of images which can be easily retrained and remember. Nwanekezi and Kalu (2012). Observed that students taught with Multimedia aids instruction have high retention scores than their counterpart who were taught with traditional teaching methods. This is so because Multimedia aids has certain features that increase the receptive and memory ability of the learner. These features are focused on the ability of the learner to learn with multiple senses, thus improve student's academic

performance, ensure learning permanency, and also improve of mental processes skills that promote deeper learning which increases the retention (Li, 2011; Oguz-Unver& Yurumezoglu, (2013).

A Multimedia aids aided instruction engaged students' interest, and encouraged them to collaborate, to inquire and to explore effectively, far beyond the bounds of the school (Galope,2013). Research has shown that people remember 20% of what they see, 40% of what they see and hear, but about 75% of what they see and hear and do simultaneously (Krishnasamy,2016). With Multimedia aids, the communication of information can be done in a more effective manner and it can be an effective instructional medium for delivering information. According to Chapman (2013), the use of Multimedia aids in teaching and learning processes has the potential to improve instruction by creating a technology-based, student-centered learning environment that allows students to take charge of their own learning. Using Multimedia aids in classroom provides students with suitable learning resources according to their learning. Thus, there is need to explore Multimedia aids package/strategy that may enhance students' performance in chemistry, hence, this study examines if teaching chemistry using Multimedia aids instructional strategy on senior school students' will improve their performance. The use of Multimedia will prevent students from rote learning and also have helped them to retain and recall what they have learnt for long period of time.

Retention on the other hand, is the ability to remember what was learnt or experienced by an individual which takes place when learning was coded into the memory through several factors. Akinbola and Folasade (2009); Ayamin and Anyachebelu (2009) argued that when teaching is characterized by rote-learning, it would be meaningless memorizing on verbalism and students make ineffective learning, and the facts thus learned are not retained. Students' retention was referred to as what could arouse and retain through the use of multimedia instructional approach (Adegoke, 2010). Alake (2015) sees retention as what is being organized and meaningful in students as they apply principles, solve problems and interpret experimental data which makes learning become effective and facts learnt are retained with passage of time.

Henceforth, it is part of the requirements of learning that, it should be retained. But the retainment should go beyond simple memory rather meaningful memory. Simple memory signifies rote-learning, but meaningful memory signifies meaningful learning. This brings about indelible meaningful learning. This means, rote-learning covers only 'remembering' which the lowest cognition stage is whereas, meaningful learning covers 'remembering', 'understanding' and 'application' stages of the cognition. As such the quest for retention ability of students become a variable of interest to researchers. Researchers were also found curious in search for means either in or outside the classroom by which students ability to regurgitate learned knowledge after a long period of time could be enhanced (Azuka, 2012). Hence, there are some things that enhance students' retention and some things that retard students' retention. Ideally, any phenomenon, materials or activities in learning situation should improve students' attainment and retention, but those phenomena that leads to confusion, misinterpretation or misconception among learning activities or materials retard the speed and efficacy and accelerates forgetting (Bichi, 2002 & Muhammad, 2011).

The conventional method in this study is one where a teacher does most of the talking, while the students listen and take notes. The method involves verbal presentation of ideas, concept, and generalization of facts. Conventional method is less tedious, save times and provides fascinating and aesthetically stimulating experience especially for the new students on topics of interest (Obeka, 2009). However, Joshi (2008) opines that lecture method is teacher-centered with little or no participation of students; consequently, they remain passive listeners. It is against this background that this study is set and examined the impact of Multimedia aids on Performance and Retention in Chemistry Secondary School Students in Funtua Educational Zone, Katsina State.

Chemistry as a science subject occupied a unique position in the scientific and technological advancement of any country in the world today (Bugaje, 2013; Ibrahim, Tairo, Aminu, Isah, Muhammad, 2017). Chemistry is an important science subject relevant for advanced studies in medical science, textile technology, agricultural science, synthetic industry, printing technology, pharmacy, chemical engineering among others (Adesoji, 2008; Edomwonyi and Avaa, 2011; Bugaje, 2013). Students must demonstrate mastery of chemistry and score at least a credit pass in WASSCE or NECO SSCE before he/she can be admitted into university to study any of the above-mentioned courses.

However, despite of the important position of Chemistry among other science related disciplines, literature has revealed that, students' Performance in Chemistry at Senior Secondary School Certificate Examination (SSCE) has been consistently poor (Njoku, 2018). In fact, Students' general performance as reported by WAEC Chief Examiners' Reports on students' performance in the 2019, 2020, 2021 2022, and 2023 examination indicate poor Performance in chemistry. Table 1 below shows the statistics of Katsina State Secondary School Students' Performance in Chemistry.

Table 1: Statistics of the Performance of Public Senior Secondary Schools' Candidates in the WASSCE (May/ June in Chemistry 2018-2023) in Katsina State

Academic Year	Total Number of Students Sat	Students with Distinction & A ₁ -C ₆	Percentage (%) D ₇ & E ₈	Pass Percentage Failure (%) F ₉
2019	25,122	14,505	57.74	42.26
2020	21,717	11,612	53.47	46.53
2021	23,916	7,188	30.06	69.94
2022	24,619	10,138	41.18	58.82
2023	22,538	9,585	42.26	57.47

Source: Department of PRS, Ministry of Education, Katsina State, Nigeria (2023)

Among the factors that contributed to the above unstable trend of students' performance in chemistry include, teachers inability to let go to the conventional method and use more of the innovative and student-centered teaching methods may have been preventing students from understanding the subjects especially the concepts that appears abstracts. It is imperative, therefore, that a more effective and innovative approach to the teaching and learning of chemistry be introduced. Hence, students' poor performance is a function of teachers' lack of usage of instructional materials like Multimedia aids to illustrate concepts perceived as difficult (Basiriyu, 2016; Abdullah, 2013). The use of Multimedia aids as instructional materials in teaching and learning situation especially in a chemistry class may play a vital role in increasing chemistry students' academic performance in Senior Secondary School, hence the study seeks to find out the Impact of Multimedia aids aids performance and Retention in Chemistry secondary school students in Funtua Zonal Educational zone Katsina State.

Objectives of the Research Problem

The objectives of this study were to:

1. Determine mean Academic Performance scores of students' taught chemistry concepts using Multimedia aids and those taught using Conventional method in Funtua Educational Zone, Katsina State.
2. Determine mean retentive ability scores of students' taught chemistry concepts using Multimedia aids and those taught using Conventional method in Funtua Educational Zone, Katsina State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the mean Academic Performance scores of students' taught chemistry concepts using Multimedia aids and those taught using Conventional method in Funtua Educational Zone, Katsina State?
2. What is the mean retention scores in of students' taught chemistry concepts using Multimedia aid and those taught using Conventional method in Funtua Educational Zone, Katsina State?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses are formulated for testing at $p \leq 0.05$ level of significance:

1. **HO₁**: There is no significant difference between mean Academic Performance scores of students' taught chemistry concepts using Multimedia aid and those taught using Conventional method in Funtua Educational Zone, Katsina State.
2. **HO₂**: There is no significant difference between mean Retention scores of students' taught chemistry concepts using Multimedia aid and those taught using Conventional method in Funtua Educational Zone, Katsina State.

Methodology

This research adopted Quasi-experimental control group research design in form of pretest, posttest, and post-posttest. This is according to Kerlinger and Leer (2005) that the design involves two groups, one group is assigned as experimental and the other group is controlled. The population of the study targeted all Students in Public Senior Secondary Schools Two (SS II) under Funtua Zonal Education Quality Assurance (FZEQA) who are offering Chemistry as a subject. The Government Public co-educational Schools were selected for use in this study because of their homogeneity, prior experiences, socio-cultural background, curriculum and population. Records of Students Returns of February 2024 of 2023/2024 Session show that the schools comprise a total number of Two thousand One Hundred and Eighty-Seven (2187) SSII students offering Chemistry as a subject. Out of which 1251 were males and 936 were females with an average age of 17 years. Ministry of Education (MOE, 2023)

In this study, multistage sampling procedure was used to select the samples for the study. It involved two stages samples. 1st stage involved cluster sampling technique which involve selection of schools in which three cluster from the 22 public senior secondary schools in Funtua Zonal Education Quality Assurance were determined. That is, each local government stand for a cluster. From each cluster, the researcher employed Simple random sample technique inform of ballot boxing in which three schools were selected from each cluster. Bakori, Danja and Funtua were the three cluster. Bakori had 8 schools, Danja had 5 school and Funtua had 9 schools. The researcher wrote and folded the names of all schools in each cluster on a piece of paper and randomly selected one school without replacements and without being bias. The three selected schools were assigned as experimental group I, and control consecutively. 2nddstage involved selection of intact classes. There were more than on arm in each school selected. Hence, the researcher wrote and folded the arms (i.e. A, B & C) therefore, simple random sampling technique was used to select two intact classes per school selected based on gender. In essence, experimental group I had two chasses: A class had 68 male and B class had 83 female students. This made the sum of 151 students. The control group also had two classes: A class had 48 male and B class had 78 female students, making up the sum of 126 students. The sample in the three groups stands at 342 students.

The instrument used for data collection was Chemistry Performance Test (CPT). The test items were adapted from West African Examination Council (WAEC), National Examination Council (NECO) and Joint Admission and Matriculation Examination (JAMB) 2002-2022 past question papers to measure the students' performance and retention in the Chemistry Concepts taught. The concepts include: Periodic table, Bonding, Hybridization, Shapes, and Polarization. The CPT has two sections (A & B) with Section 'A' elicits for Bio data (Name of School, Class & Gender) of the respondent, while Section 'B' composed of forty (40) Multiple Choice Questions of which respondents are expected to provide the correct answer to each item. Each item is associated with four options. The CPT was used on the Experimental and Control Groups at pre-test, post-test and post-post-test (retention test). The items in CPT were constructed to suit the six cognitive levels based on Blooms' Taxonomy for the Cognitive Domains. The instruments and instructional plans were validated by experts in the Departments of Science and Vocational Education, Department of Pure and Industrial Chemistry, Umaru Musa Yaradua University, Katsina, Nigeria. The CPT was pilot tested in Government College Pilot Senior Secondary School SSII Chemistry Students (which is not part of the sample) twice within an interval of two weeks. Test-retest Method was used to assess the reliability of the CPT. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) statistical tool was employed for analysis. The reliability coefficient of CPT was found to be $r = 0.86$ which indicates high reliability index. Hence, reliable for in this study. At the schools visited, the researcher pre-tested the students using CPT for both Experimental and Control Groups before any treatment.

After the pre-test, for Control Class, the research assistant taught the Chemistry Concepts (Periodic table, Bonding, Hybridization, Shapes and Polarization) to the students for the duration of six (6) weeks, forty-five (45) minutes per week using conventional Method. For experimental class, the treatment involved teaching of the same Chemistry Concepts for the same duration using Multimedia aids Lesson Plans. The Multimedia aids Lesson Plan was developed by the researcher in accordance with Multimedia aids-based Approach adapted from (Mayer, 2013). Multimedia aids Instructional Guide Framework is a six steps sequence of a logical operations with the first stage begins with the teacher's task of introducing the concept to be taught to the students briefly. The researcher taught Periodic table using computer and projector and order to help the student understand the concept and attract the attention of the students. The researcher used the same method and taught Periodic table, Chemical bonding, Hybridization, Shapes and Polarization for six weeks

After the six (6) weeks teaching (Treatment Session), the Experimental and Control Groups, posttest was administered using reoriented and reordered CPT to both groups (for gain determination, if any). Two consecutive weeks later, CPT items were reoriented and re-reordered and administered to both Experimental and Control groups (for retention determination, if any). The CPT scripts were marked by the researcher according to the groups (EG and CG) using appropriate Marking Scheme. The two research questions were answered using Mean and Standard Deviation (SD) whereas hypotheses one and two were tested using an Independent Samples t-test at 0.05 level of significance using Statistical Package for Social Science Software Version 23.1.

Results

Presentations in this section are based on research questions and hypotheses:

1. **Research Question One:** What is the mean Academic Performance scores of students' taught chemistry concepts using Multimedia aid and those taught using Conventional method in Funtua Educational Zone, Katsina State?

To answer research question one, the post-test scores of students for CPT in the control and experimental group were subjected to descriptive statistics in form of Means and Standard Deviations. This is presented in Table 2

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics of CPT Scores of the and Experimental Group and Control

Variable	Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean Difference
Performance	Experimental	151	19.64	3.357	4.40
	Control	126	15.24	2.260	

Table 2 revealed that the mean difference between the CPT Scores of EG ($m = 19.64$, $SD = 3.357$) and that of the CG ($m = 15.24$, $SD = 2.260$) is 4.40. It could therefore be seen that EG outperformed the CG.

Research Question Two:

What is the mean retention scores in of students’ taught chemistry concepts using Multimedia aid and those taught using Conventional method in Funtua Educational Zone, Katsina State?

To answer research question two, the post posttest cores of students for CPT in the control and experimental group were subjected to descriptive statistics in form of Means and Standard Deviations. This is presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics of CPT Scores of the Experimental Group and Control

Variable	Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean Difference
Retention	Experimental	151	17.21	4.067	2.20
	Control	126	15.01	2.411	

Table 3: revealed that the mean difference between the CPT Scores of EG ($m = 17.21$, $SD = 4.067$) and that of the CG ($m = 15.01$, $SD = 2.411$) is 2.20 . It could therefore be seen that EG outperformed the CG

Hypotheses

The following null hypothesis were tested at 0.05 level of significance

H0₁:

There is no significant difference between mean Academic Performance scores of students’ taught chemistry concepts using Multimedia aid and those taught using Conventional method in Funtua Educational Zone, Katsina State.

In order to test hypothesis one, the post- test of experimental and control groups for CPT were subjected to t-test of independent sample statistics. Summary of the analysis was presented in table 4

Table 4: t-test analysis of the Posttest for CPT of Control and Experimental Group

Groups	N	Mean	SD	Df	t-value	P-value	Decision
Experimental	151	19.64	3.357	275	9.72	0.00	Significant
Control	126	15.24	2.260				

Table 4 revealed that the difference between the mean Posttest CPT Scores of EG₁ ($m = 19.54$, $SD = 3.387$) and that of the CG ($m = 15.24$, $SD = 2.260$) is significant [$t(275) = 9.72$, $P < 0.05$ based on the decision rule, this study rejected the null hypothesis one (1) that says there is no significant difference in mean academic performance scores in Periodic table between students taught using Multimedia aids and those taught using lecture method.. The decision implies that, there is a significant difference in mean academic performance scores in Periodic table between students taught using Multimedia aids and those taught using lecture method. This indicates that the students of experimental group performed significantly better than control group after treatment with Multimedia aids

H₀₂:

There is no significant difference between mean Retention scores of students’ taught chemistry concepts using Multimedia aid and those taught using Conventional method in Funtua Educational Zone, Katsina State. In order to test hypothesis two, the post posttest of experimental and control groups for CPT were subjected to t-test of independent sample statistics. Summary of the analysis was presented in table 5

Table 5: -test analysis of the Post-Posttest for CPT of Control and Experimental Group

Groups	N	Mean	SD	Df	t-value	P-value	Decision
Experimental	151	20.80	3.78	275	6.28	0.00	Significant
Control	126	15.48	2.89				

Table 5 revealed that the difference between the mean Post-Posttest CPT Scores of EG₁ (m = 20.80, SD= 3.78) and that of the CG (m= 15.48, SD= 2.89) is significant [t(275) = 6.28, P < 0.05 based on the decision rule, this study rejected the null hypothesis three (3) that says there is no significant difference in the mean retention scores in Periodic table between students taught using Multimedia aids and those taught using lecture method. The decision implies that, there is a significant difference in the mean retention scores in Periodic table between students taught using Multimedia aids and those taught using lecture method. This indicates that the students of experimental group performed significantly better than control group in the mean retention scores in Periodic table after treatment with Multimedia aids.

Discussion of the Finding

The result from the research question one and testing of hypothesis one, it indicated that the experimental group who were taught chemistry concepts using Multimedia aids-based Approach achieved significantly better than those in the control group who were taught same concepts using conventional method. This indicates that Multimedia aids-based Approach is more effective in enhancing chemistry students’ academic performance in chemistry concepts than the conventional method of teaching. This finding is in line with that of Akinbadewa (2020) investigated the Effectiveness of Multimedia aids Instructional Learning Packages in Enhancing Secondary School Student’s Attitudes towards Chemistry.

From the finding of Research Question Two proved that Students from experimental group retained chemistry concepts taught using Multimedia aids-based Approach better than those taught same concepts using conventional method. In addition, Null Hypothesis Two was rejected based on analysis of t-test independent sample which confirms that significant difference exists in the retention scores of students taught chemistry concepts using Multimedia aids-based Approach and those taught using Conventional method. This indicates that the potentiality of Multimedia aids-based Approach to teaching chemistry concepts in enhancing retention ability of students. This finding is in line with that of Hurmuzan and Yahya (2015) conducted a study titled Effects of Multimedia aids Resources on Student’s Academic performances and retention in social studies in Junior Secondary Schools, Kaduna State- Nigeria. The following are the major findings of this study:

1. There is a significant difference in mean academic performance scores in Chemistry between students taught using Multimedia aids and those taught using conventional method in Funtua Zone Katsina State
2. There is a significant difference in the mean retention scores in Chemistry between students taught using Multimedia aids and those taught using conventional method in Funtua Zone Katsina State.

Conclusions

This study was conducted as part of the efforts of educational researchers in promoting the appropriate, relevant and suitable pedagogy in teaching chemistry which will help in addressing issues related to student’s academic performance and retention in Chemistry. Based on the findings of the study, it can be concluded that Multimedia aids-based approach is effective in enhancing students’ performance and retention in chemistry.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made from the findings of the study.

1. Teachers at senior secondary schools should expose Chemistry students to Multimedia aids to promote their academic performance in the subject.

2. Science teachers should incorporate the use Multimedia aids in Chemistry and other science subjects
3. Multimedia aids should be incorporated in the curriculum of teacher training institutions to promote retention ability in Chemistry.

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